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All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture

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Contents

1. Introduction.....	7
2. The Four IMTA and Society Workshops	9
2.1 Scotland	9
2.2 South Africa	10
2.3 Brazil	11
2.4 Argentina	14
3. Risks and Opportunities: Exploring Barriers and Incentives	17
3.1 Method	17
3.2 Results	17
3.2.1 Scotland	17
3.2.2 South Africa	21
3.2.3 Brazil	24
3.2.4 Argentina	25
3.3 Conclusion	31
4. Consumer Preferences	32
4.1 Method	32
4.2 Results	32
4.2.1 Scotland	32
4.2.2 South Africa	34
4.2.3 Brazil	36
4.2.4 Argentina	39
5. Social Licence Guidelines.....	42
5.1 Method	42
5.2 Results	44
5.2.1 Scotland	44
5.2.2 South Africa	45
5.2.3 Brazil	46
	3

5.2.4. Argentina	47
5.3 Conclusion	49
6. Policy	50
6.1 Method	50
6.2 Results	51
6.2.1 Scotland	51
6.2.2 South Africa	53
6.2.3 Brazil	54
6.2.4. Argentina	56
7. Conclusion and Next Steps	59

List of Figures (Hyperlinked)

[Fig. 1: Screenshot from the Scotland online workshop.](#)

[Fig. 2: Screenshot from the South Africa online workshop.](#)

[Fig. 3: Luis Poersch, Federal University of Rio Grande, introduces the ASTRAL project and presents ASTRAL activities in Brazil.](#)

[Fig. 4: Guest presentation from David Basset, General Secretary of EATiP.](#)

[Fig. 5: Tomás Chalde, CADIC-CONICET, introduces the ASTRAL project and presents ASTRAL activities in Argentina.](#)

[Fig. 6: Marine Desoche, Crowdhelix, introduces participants to the Aquaculture Helix.](#)

[Fig. 7: Tamara Rubilar, manager at Erisea, giving a presentation about her aquaculture activities and products.](#)

[Fig. 8: The complete matrix of social risks and opportunities – Scotland.](#)

[Fig. 9: The complete matrix of social risks and opportunities – South Africa.](#)

[Fig. 10: The complete matrix of social risks and opportunities – Brazil.](#)

[Fig.11: The Jamboard matrix for the risks and opportunities activity in Brazil.](#)

[Fig. 12: The complete matrix of social risks and opportunities – Argentina.](#)

[Fig. 13: Participants at the Argentina workshop adding to the matrix for the risks and opportunities activity.](#)

[Fig. 14: Response to the first question in the consumer preferences activity – Scotland.](#)

[Fig. 15: Response to the second question in the consumer preferences activity – Scotland.](#)

[Fig. 16: Response to the third question in the consumer preferences activity – Scotland.](#)

[Fig. 17: Response to the first question in the consumer preferences activity – South Africa.](#)

[Fig. 18: Response to the second question in the consumer preferences activity – South Africa.](#)

[Fig. 19: Response to the third question in the consumer preferences activity – South Africa.](#)

[Fig. 20: Daniel Checa Alias, Leitat Technological Institute, presenting the consumer preferences activity in the Brazil workshop.](#)

[Fig. 21: Response to the first question in the consumer preferences activity – Brazil.](#)

[Fig. 22: Response to the second question in the consumer preferences activity – Brazil.](#)

[Fig. 23: Response to the third question in the consumer preferences activity – Brazil.](#)

[Fig. 24: Response to the first question in the consumer preferences activity – Argentina.](#)

[Fig. 25: Response to the second question in the consumer preferences activity – Argentina.](#)

[Fig. 26: Response to the third question in the consumer preferences activity – Argentina.](#)

[Fig. 27: Results of the social licence guidelines activity in Argentina.](#)

[Fig. 28: Laura Ferguson, SAMS, discusses the social licence activity with participants at the Argentina workshop.](#)

[Fig. 29: The policy activity Jamboard.](#)

[Fig. 30: Joel Armengol Pagès, Leitat Technological Institute, leads the policy discussion as Tomás Chalde, CADIC-CONICET, positions notes on the board.](#)

[Fig. 31: Completed policy Jamboard for Scotland.](#)

[Fig. 32: Completed policy Jamboard for South Africa.](#)

[Fig. 33: Policy matrix for Brazil Group 1.](#)

[Fig. 34: Policy matrix for Brazil Group 2.](#)

[Fig. 35: Policy matrix for Brazil Group 3.](#)

[Fig. 36: Completed policy Jamboard for Argentina.](#)

List of Tables (Hyperlinked)

[Table 1: Stakeholder group numbers for the Scotland workshop.](#)

[Table 2: Stakeholder group numbers for the South Africa workshop.](#)

[Table 3: Stakeholder group numbers for the Brazil workshop.](#)

[Table 4: Stakeholder group numbers for the Argentina workshop.](#)

List of Appendices (Hyperlinked)

[Appendix I: Agenda for ASTRAL IMTA and Society Workshop: Scotland](#)

[Appendix II: Agenda for ASTRAL IMTA and Society Workshop: South Africa](#)

[Appendix III: Agenda for ASTRAL IMTA and Society Workshop: Brazil](#)

[Appendix IV: Agenda for ASTRAL IMTA and Society Workshop: Argentina](#)

[Appendix V: Workshop invitation email template \(edited/translated to local language for each event\)](#)

[Appendix VI: Workshop online link email template \(for online workshops\)](#)

[Appendix VII: Participant information sheet](#)

[Appendix VIII: Consent form](#)

1. Introduction

ASTRAL is a European Union Horizon 2020 collaborative project that focuses on Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) farming. ASTRAL's main aim is to develop new, sustainable, profitable and resilient value chains for IMTA within the framework of existing, emerging and potential Atlantic markets. Further information about the project can be found at <https://www.astral-project.eu/>.

This report on public perception and awareness of IMTA describes the assessment of public perception and awareness of IMTA at four ASTRAL sites. It is based on the results of the ASTRAL project's series of IMTA and Society Workshops, the fulfilment of *Task 7.6.1 Participatory Workshops*, that were held online and in person between October 2021 and November 2022 at the following locations:

Scotland, 22nd October 2021 (online)

South Africa, 15th February 2022 (online)

Brazil, 31st August 2022 (in person as an event at IV International Fish Congress & Fish Expo Brazil 2022, Foz do Iguaçu)

Argentina, 8th November 2022 (in person at CADIC-CONICET, Ushuaia)

The main aim of the workshops was to consult the full range of identified stakeholders, gathering their views on perceptions of IMTA. The workshops were designed for interested parties to engage with the ASTRAL project, learn more about it and participate in a series of discussions that would contribute to ASTRAL project tasks and outputs on perceptions of IMTA, Social Licence to Operate, consumer preferences and policy. Activities were planned for groups of 20- 30 in attendance, although significantly more invites were sent out as it was anticipated many would be unable or not wish to participate. The practicalities of running a very large session and the dynamics of social science methods, predominantly based on contextually rich discussion, favour groups not in excess of 30 persons. The attendance at the Scotland and Brazil workshops, 13 and 16 respectively, was lower than ideal. There are always challenges in recruiting volunteers to participate in such events, as we are dependent to a large extent on their goodwill. Nevertheless, all workshops were attended by a broad range of stakeholder groups, including local NGOs, community members, regulatory agencies, politicians, producers and researchers, and discussions flowed well. The data collected provides valuable information due to the inclusion of individuals across this social spectrum, with representatives from all of the relevant stakeholders invited to contribute at each location. The

findings are non-generalisable, yet thematically useful and comparable across case studies. Further details on the organisation and attendance of the individual workshops are presented in Section 2.

Prior to the workshops commencing, an information sheet (Appendix VII) was distributed to all participants and signed consent forms (Appendix VIII) were collected. At the opening of each workshop, attendees were welcomed and given a presentation introducing the ASTRAL project, outlining the project work in the local region and exploring social aspects of IMTA, followed by some slides introducing the first activity. There were four participatory activities at each workshop. The first explored participants' perceptions of IMTA with a focus on the anticipated risks and opportunities associated with IMTA, providing information on social barriers and incentives to IMTA. The second activity was a short and engaging survey on consumer preferences, intended to expose how participants would consume IMTA products. The third activity built on the foundations of what was discussed in the first activity. In it, participants were invited to contribute to the development of social licence guidelines (associated with *Task 7.6.2 Co-developing Interactive Guidelines*) by explaining what behaviours, practices and regulation they would like to see in order for producers to gain Social Licence to Operate (SLO) for IMTA. The fourth and final activity was a session on policy issues (associated with *Task 7.7 Studies on Governance, Policy, Food Safety/Consumer Trust and Social Acceptability*), designed to highlight which policy matters were of most importance to IMTA stakeholders. Further details on the methodology of each activity are provided in the relevant sections of this report (Sections 3-6).

For the latter two, in-person, workshops the order the activities were presented in was slightly altered and there were also some improvements in the delivery of some tasks for them, but the form and content remained broadly the same, to ensure the results were comparable. Alterations from the original format are described in Section 2 and Sections 3-6 where relevant.

Following each of the regional workshops, reports of the results were disseminated to participants of those workshops who had indicated an interest in receiving them through supplying their email address.

The structure of this report broadly follows the structure of the workshops. Section 2 first presents details of each of the workshops, including the location, the partners involved and the stakeholders in attendance. The following sections, from Section 3 through to Section 6, present the methodology and results for each of the participatory activities in turn. Finally, Section 7 presents the conclusion and next steps.

2. The Four IMTA and Society Workshops

2.1 Scotland

The ASTRAL IMTA and Society: Scotland workshop was hosted by the Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS) and held on 22nd October 2021. Due to persisting uncertainties surrounding social mixing regulations during the COVID-19 pandemic, this event was held online via Microsoft Teams.

At the opening of the workshop, attendees were welcomed and given a presentation introducing the ASTRAL project, the Port-a-Bhuiltin IMTA lab and researching social aspects of IMTA. This presentation was given by Laura Ferguson from SAMS, who also introduced and chaired the risks and opportunities and social licence guidelines, activities. The consumer preference and policy activities were chaired by colleagues from Leitid Technological Institute, Joel Armengol Pagès and Cristina Yacoub López, respectively. The workshop was concluded with a presentation on the Aquaculture Helix by Marine Desoche from Crowdhelix. The agenda for the workshop is included as Appendix I.

Fig. 1: Screenshot from the Scotland online workshop.

A broad range of stakeholders were invited by SAMS, including government organisations, producers, NGOs and community groups. On the day, there were 13 stakeholders in attendance and the workshop lasted 2 hours and 30 minutes. The numbers for stakeholder groups in attendance are displayed in Table 1. As it was held online, the workshop was recorded and transcribed, assisting the analysis of the data. The transcript was anonymised, and the recording subsequently deleted. Direct quotes from this transcript can be found in this report to illustrate some of the findings.

Stakeholder Group	Number
Community interest group	2
Local politician	2
Aquaculture industry	2
Fisheries representative	2
Regulator	1
Policymaker	1
NGO	2
Nature restoration	1
Total	13

Table 1: Stakeholder group numbers for the Scotland workshop.

2.2 South Africa

The ASTRAL IMTA and Society: South Africa workshop was hosted by the University of Cape Town (UCT) and took place on 15th February 2022. As with the Scotland workshop, it was held online via Microsoft Teams due to continuing concerns over the transmission of COVID-19 and potentially changing social restrictions.

The South Africa workshop followed a very similar format to the Scotland workshop, owing to its success. John Bolton (UCT) opened with a presentation introducing the ASTRAL project and work on it in South Africa. Presentations on social aspects of IMTA and Social Licence to Operate were given by Laura Ferguson (SAMS). The consumer preference and policy activities were again chaired by Joel Armengol Pagès and Cristina Yacoub López (Leitat Technological Institute), respectively. Marine Desoche (CrowdHelix) ended the workshop presentations on the topic of the Aquaculture Helix. The agenda for the workshop is included as Appendix II.

Fig. 2: Screenshot from the South Africa online workshop.

31 stakeholders, shown in Table 2, attended the South Africa workshop, which was 2 hours 30 minutes in duration.

Stakeholder Group	Number
Aquaculture industry	12
Academia/Research	12
Government	4
Community	1
Financial sector	1
Retailer	1
Total	31

Table 2: Stakeholder group numbers for the South Africa workshop.

As with the Scotland workshop, this event was recorded, transcribed and anonymised. Direct quotes from this transcript were included in this report.

2.3 Brazil

The ASTRAL IMTA and Society: Brazil workshop was the first that operated as an in-person event. It took place on 31st August 2022 as an event at IV International Fish Congress & Fish Expo Brazil 2022 in Foz do Iguaçu, Brazil, and was hosted by the Federal University of Rio Grande (FURG). There were 16 participants. Data on the categories of stakeholders in attendance at the Brazil workshop is given in Table 3.

Stakeholder Group	Number
Academia/Research	7
Fish congress	2
Enterprise agency	1
Government department	1
Aquaculture organisation	1
Unknown	4
Total	16

Table 3: Stakeholder group numbers for the Brazil workshop.

Some adjustments were made for the transition to in-person events, including expansion of the workshop to 4 hours. More time was allocated to activities, and brief round-table introductions and a guest presentation were included. Additionally, this was the first workshop to use a language other than English. It was conducted in Portuguese with English translation available for those on the ASTRAL team who required it.

After a brief welcome and opening remarks, Luis Poersch (FURG) gave a presentation on the ASTRAL project and associated activities in Brazil, including some recent results from his work. This was followed by the first activity, on risks and opportunities associated with IMTA, which was chaired by Laura Ferguson (SAMS), as in previous workshops. After the conclusion of the first activity, the social licence guidelines activity was introduced with a new format for the in-person workshops. Instead of the discussion to draw out guidelines, workshop participants were each given three post-it notes and asked to write down guidelines for gaining and maintaining Social Licence to Operate for IMTA. Later in the workshop, after the results had been gathered and emergent themes identified, the suggested guidelines were discussed with the participants. This was intended to make the activity more active, colourful and easier to work with the language barrier between the English-speaking leader of the activity (Laura Ferguson, SAMS) and the Portuguese-speaking participants. The other activities remained in the same digital format as previous workshops, with live discussions. Marine Desoche (CrowdHelix) then presented her introduction to the Aquaculture Helix prior to the networking break. This was followed by the consumer preferences and policy activities, led by Daniel Checa Alias (Leitat Technological Institute).

Fig. 3: Luis Poersch, Federal University of Rio Grande, introduces the ASTRAL project and presents ASTRAL activities in Brazil.

The workshop concluded with a guest presentation from David Basset, General Secretary of EATiP – European Aquaculture Technology and Innovation Platform (EATiP) on his work, with a focus on Brazil. The agenda is included as Appendix III.

Due to a lack of suitable recording equipment at the venue, this workshop was not recorded and there is no transcript to supplement the results.

Fig. 4: Guest presentation from David Basset, General Secretary of EATiP.

2.4 Argentina

The ASTRAL IMTA and Society: Argentina workshop was the second to operate as an in-person event. It took place on 8th November 2022 at Centro Austral de Investigaciones Científicas (CADIC-CONICET), Ushuaia. The duration of 4 hours that had been adopted for the Brazil workshop was repeated for the Argentina event. It was held in Spanish with English translation for those on the ASTRAL *Task 7.6 Sharing Knowledge With and For Society* team in attendance who required it.

Tomás Chalde (CADIC-CONICET) opened the workshop with an introduction to ASTRAL and a presentation on ASTRAL work in Argentina, and initiated 30 second round the room introductions. Laura Ferguson (SAMS) then gave a presentation on IMTA and society, in English with translation into Spanish, which ended with an introduction to the risks and opportunities activity.

Fig. 5: Tomás Chalde, CADIC-CONICET, introduces the ASTRAL project and presents ASTRAL activities in Argentina.

The workshop activities were all the same as in the Brazil workshop, with the exception of post-it notes on a whiteboard substituting for the online Jamboard for the policy and risks and opportunities activities at the Argentina workshop, due to concerns about access to reliable internet connectivity for all attendees, and a move away from the discussion-led format for the risks and opportunities activity, due to difficulties with two-way translation that had become apparent in Brazil. The risks and opportunities matrix and social licence guidelines activities were led by Laura Ferguson (SAMS), as in

all previous workshops in the series. The consumer preference and policy activities were led by Joel Armengol Pagès (Leitat Technological Institute). As with all previous workshops, Marine Desoche (Crowdhelix) gave a presentation on the Aquaculture Helix. Tamara Rubilar, a scientific researcher at the Center for the Study of Marine Systems (CESIMAR-CENPAT-CONICET) and the manager of the Base Technology Enterprise Erisea, also gave a presentation about the sea urchin aquaculture centre and the product she produces at it. The agenda for the workshop is included as Appendix IV.

Fig. 6: Marine Desoche, Crowdhelix, introduces participants to the Aquaculture Helix.

Fig. 7: Tamara Rubilar, manager at Erisea, giving a presentation about her aquaculture activities and products.

The Argentina workshop was attended by 22 stakeholders, as specified in Table 4. All were awarded a certificate of attendance.

Stakeholder Group	Number
Academia/research	9
Decision maker (2 also research)	5
Student	3
Fisheries representative (also research)	1
Aquaculture industry (also research)	1
Aquaculture association (also research)	1
Government	1
R&D institution	1
Total	22

Table 4: Stakeholder group numbers for the Argentina workshop.

The Argentina event was recorded and there is a Spanish language transcript. Due to the change in format of the risks and opportunities and social licence guidelines activities away from the discussion model, there is no additional material for these to report. The transcript will mainly be used to provide context to the policy activity for *Task 7.7 Studies on Governance, Policy, Food Safety/Consumer Trust and Social Acceptability*, which will be reported in *Deliverable 7.7 Policy Recommendations*.

3. Risks and Opportunities: Exploring Barriers and Incentives

3.1 Method

The first interactive activity explored public perceptions of IMTA through the identification of perceived risks and opportunities that may form social barriers and incentives for IMTA. This part of the workshop was based on a discussion of the social risks and opportunities that participants associate with IMTA, with results recorded using a bespoke matrix on Google Jamboard. In the case of the Argentina workshop, results were initially recorded with post-it notes on a projected copy of the Jamboard, then translated and added to the electronic version afterwards.

On the x-axis of the matrix was time, measured in short term, medium term and long term. On the y-axis was impact, measured as low impact, medium impact and high impact. Participants were invited to put digital notes on the board (paper notes in the case of the Argentina workshop) showing what they perceived to be the social risks and opportunities arising from IMTA development in the local area. They placed the notes on the grid according to what level of impact and timescale they expected them to be relevant to. A risk/opportunity can appear in several boxes, for example in Scotland visual impact featured in all of the short, medium and long terms. In the first three workshops, this activity was discussion-led with a facilitated discussion for all participants, and in the Argentina workshop, participants were simply invited to place their notes themselves, with the results summarised and reported afterwards. This decision was based on difficulties experienced in Brazil with holding a two-way discussion when the chair and participants require translation between each other. It was considered the alternative format would provide a smoother and better experience for attendees, as well as encourage everyone to participate by issuing three sticky notes, as opposed to requesting contributions via the discussion.

3.2 Results

3.2.1 Scotland

The completed matrix from the Scotland workshop is shown in Figure 8. The matrix results have been supplemented by information from the transcript of the activity's discussion. The red notes indicate

risks, the green notes indicate opportunities and the orange note was used for “data and transparency” as the participant felt there could be both a risk and an opportunity associated with it. Participants foresaw opportunity from the sharing of data aiding progress and for basing decisions on strong data, but also risk that data could be used for other purposes or be made available to the extent it becomes a threat to businesses.

Risks & Opportunities: Exploring Social Barriers & Incentives to Social Licence

Fig. 8: The complete matrix of social risks and opportunities – Scotland.

The first topic raised was risk of interaction with other marine users and constraints on space, in particular with fishing grounds and fishing in general, which was anticipated would be of high impact in all of the short, medium and long terms as the fishing industry is already being squeezed by various sea users. Entanglement is also a big issue currently, with a number of problems being reported, and it is an increasing problem – not just getting caught up mooring lines which may not be clearly marked, but also equipment which breaks away in heavy weather and is partially submerged. There is a campaign to see that all equipment from aquaculture sites should be clearly marked with the details of the owner so that at least they can be notified should anybody find the equipment on the shore, come across it in the sea or if there’s an entanglement issue.

The visual impact was then discussed. Long term, it was said the visual impact could be quite high. One participant noted that the longer a fish farm or aquaculture site is in a location, the more it tends to gather a lot of debris. Visual impact was described as a controversial topic because there is a division

of people who think that aquaculture sites are really not very pleasing to the eye, but there are others who say that it actually fits suitably with the new scene of the coast. For the local economy, particularly in fragile areas of which there are many in the West Coast of Scotland, aquaculture has now become a necessary part of the landscape, regardless of views on the visual impact.

Another risk raised was the potential impact of unknowns in relation to IMTA and the resulting need to fill in evidence gaps. It was stressed, however, that it is important to consider these in terms of the known environmental impacts of more established practices and the benefits of IMTA in comparison.

A big opportunity stressed, considering the age that we live in now, with biodiversity loss and the climate emergency, is that anything that sequesters carbon and that cleans the water such as native oysters and kelp farms is something communities are very open to because of the environmental benefits. IMTA is an opportunity for better marine management and that is perceived as something communities could really support.

Sustainability of the local economy was also raised as an opportunity associated with IMTA. Not only could it bring a lot of new employment to the area, but major companies would also invest in local communities and in local services, infrastructure and other developments. IMTA, in particular, was perceived to increase the diversity and sustainability of aquaculture and the wider local marine industries, making them more resilient:

“IMTA clearly has the ability to increase the diversity of aquaculture but also possibly improve interactions with fisheries, for example. There is scope for looking at how aquaculture installations can accommodate, for example, static gear interests potentially and take advantage of aggregated target commercial species, but the thing about increased diversity is it adds resilience to the local economy. It removes the reliance on one or two industries and the fragility that goes along with that... So, whether the salmon farming hangs around or evolves and moves offshore or something like that, what they have managed to establish are other businesses or other provider opportunities for others.”

Related to this would be up-skilling of the local community, in turn making it more resilient. It was also thought IMTA could contribute to helping counter rural depopulation.

The idea of social licence came under discussion. One participant thought there was an overwhelming distrust about the term social licence because they believe many objectors, whom they did not state

individually, have not been included in the planning process for aquaculture sites and are largely overruled. They identified a lack of proper consultation and honesty about what's happening. Early consultation was stressed as necessary, and communication in an accessible language was also highlighted as important because if the language isn't accessible and other stakeholders can't engage with it properly, that can defeat the purpose of any engagement activities that take place.

Another key point raised by a participant was that *"if you're thinking about IMTA you're bringing together a series of sectors and they've likely already, to some extent, established their own social licence or not and I think that by bringing them all together you need to take that into account."*

The need to diverge from old relationships and old stakeholder practices was emphasised:

"IMTA or any other development in the marine environment can't proceed on the basis of winners and losers because ultimately it will stall. And we see that already in some of the comments that you've made. And social licence is integral to that. Social licence will only come about when there are not perceived to be clear winners and clear losers and all the sort of animosities that arise from that. Like I say, it is a changing environment, and it does need a calibration of how we work in the marine environment."

From the completed matrix (Fig. 8), it is evident the majority of perceived opportunities associated with IMTA appear in the long term, with a few in the medium term and only one in the short term. The workshop participants were confident that IMTA opportunities would have a high positive impact, but that these benefits would take a long time to be felt. Crucially, the long term opportunities include those that would benefit the local community and help gain social licence, such as employment, more resilient businesses, a more sustainable local economy and a reduction in depopulation. In contrast, the perceived risks are spread out across the short, medium and long terms, suggesting it is thought that local communities, marine users and other stakeholders will be subject to the negative impacts long before any positive impacts are felt. Visual impact, spatial overlap, entanglement, lack of consultation with fishermen and the risks associated with adopting a new system were all expected to be high impact risks that would be faced at the outset of an IMTA development, with many, such as visual impact spatial overlap and entanglement, continuing into the long term. These would then be accompanied by developing risks, for example environmental impacts (some unknown), overlapping interests and possible negative effects on business resilience. These results highlight the areas of interest and concern for stakeholders in Scotland with regards to IMTA development, and indicate what may be of importance in creating guidelines for Social Licence to Operate.

3.2.2 South Africa

The completed matrix from the South Africa workshop is shown in Figure 9. The matrix results have been supplemented by information from the transcript of the activity’s discussion.

Risks & Opportunities: Exploring Social Barriers & Incentives to Social Licence

Fig. 9: The complete matrix of social risks and opportunities – South Africa.

The first topic raised among workshop participants was the risk of biosecurity with IMTA and recirculation technologies, especially when secondary crops are being produced:

“There’s a lot of people that regard that as potentially high risk. So, people are concerned about that, so I think that has probably hampered a little bit of development in terms of adopting some of these IMTA technologies, at least locally.”

Next, the topic of visual impact was discussed. It was suggested that minimising the visual impact of a facility can be beneficial if you want to look at the bay but it also can be a problem navigationally. If you want to sail a yacht, for example, you would prefer to be able to see a farm clearly to ensure that you miss it. Therefore, visual impact can have two different points of view and it is a challenge to deal with that in this sort of system.

Marketing was also a topic that related both to risks and opportunities. On the positive side, it was said IMTA was associated with a green marketing opportunity. On the other side, there were concerns about negative perceptions of aquaculture in general and specific IMTA concerns regarding people's resistance to eating products that feed on waste. It was, however, suggested that negative perceptions were predominantly a short term risk, as they typically abate over time and people tend to get more used to it and more supportive of it:

"There is always a bit of a negative perception at the start before they know what to expect and it's always better to reject something than accept something that you don't know, but over time as people notice that there is no actual real impact, you know, all is not as bad as they feared, that sort of perception definitely changes."

Another risk raised was the lack of skills, particularly initially when setting up a new farm - not having enough people that have the necessary skills to implement IMTA technologies, and even aquaculture in general:

"I think that in South Africa, most of our aquaculture operations are in the rural areas where there's not a high level of education and it's very difficult to always source the experience and expertise that you need and you have to end up to do a lot of in-house training. Certainly, a lack of sort of foundation of education to build upon in South Africa, specifically, I think is quite a big challenge."

Lack of market for new products was also raised as a wider risk for IMTA. With some of the additional products, people don't want to grow them if they can't sell them and that's one of the poor selling points for a number of species that may potentially be used in IMTA.

The discussion was rounded off with a particularly interesting perspective on the definition of IMTA, placing it within wider sustainability measures in the aquaculture industry:

"I think when you grow a product and your one product is reliant on the other it complicates the production process, even though the perception is great, you know that you're making one product from the waste of another, but for instance if one has to consider there's a massive project, for instance, on the Namibian west coast at the moment growing kelp offshore for carbon credits. I think, it fills all the requirements in terms of sustainability but it's a product on its own. So, algae or secondary products don't need to be linked to an abalone farm, for instance, or a fish farm. They can be stand-

alone products and still tick all the boxes in terms of environmental sustainability and I don't know whether that falls into the terms and conditions of the IMTA project, but I think it needs to be considered that there are other environmentally sustainable and green initiatives that are stand-alone projects."

"I'd just also further something brought up a moment ago, whether what [the previous speaker] was describing falls under the definition of IMTA and I'd say it certainly does. So, for example, growing kelp. Just because you're not growing it in the immediate vicinity of another farm doesn't mean that you're not contributing to IMTA because IMTA more broadly can be looked at from an ecosystem point of view as well and not necessarily from a single farm point of view and a very small location. You can actually take a step back and apply the same concept to a more ecosystems approach, and more people are doing that and, in fact, if you ask the guys that know more about IMTA than myself, they'll tell you that it shouldn't be defined. It needs to be interpreted way more broadly. So, I would respond [to the previous speaker] by saying that what he described certainly is an example of IMTA but just on a larger scale and looking at it from an ecosystem approach as opposed to just a single farm."

This concluded the discussion for the activity on social risks and opportunities. As can be seen from the completed matrix (Fig. 9), most are in the medium and high boxes and this shows us that IMTA is perceived to be quite impactful on society in South Africa. The risks appear quite evenly spread across the short, medium and long terms, but the opportunities are placed mostly in the medium and long terms.

A large proportion of participants in this workshop were aquaculture producers. This is reflected in their response to this exercise, which in many cases focused on risks to and opportunities for producers as opposed to society. Many responses focused on the market, in terms of a potential lack of a market, market perception or market acceptance. Other participants cited concerns about lack of farm space, lack of knowledge or skills to practice IMTA and barriers to entry for small enterprises. On social aspects, skills development, economic resilience, healthy diets and environmental benefits were all specified as opportunities, while risks were focused on visual impact, conflict of interests and economic sustainability.

3.2.3 Brazil

The completed matrix from the Brazil workshop is shown in Figure 10.

Riscos & Oportunidades: Explorando as barreiras sociais e Incentivos à licença social

Fig. 10: The complete matrix of social risks and opportunities – Brazil.

There is no transcript material for this activity at the Brazil workshop, therefore less detail can be reported.

One of the most significant aspects discussed by participants was related to job creation. It was anticipated that IMTA would lead to an increasing number of new jobs and local business opportunities as time progresses. Unlike with the Scotland and South Africa workshops, participants in this activity at the Brazil workshop anticipated opportunities from IMTA to be observable from the outset, although the level of impact from them was expected to increase as time progresses. Risks relating to environmental impacts were the most frequent type of concern raised in the discussion of risks. These were not expected to diminish over time – one participant even anticipated they would increase steadily from the short to long term.

Fig.11: The Jamboard matrix for the risks and opportunities activity in Brazil.

3.2.4 Argentina

The completed matrix from the Argentina workshop is shown in Figure 12. As the response to this exercise in Argentina was large and the notes have had to be made exceptionally small to fit in the grid, they have also been displayed in text below. As discussed previously, there is no discussion transcript associated with the results for this activity from the Argentina workshop, due to the change in format of the activity.

Risks & Opportunities: Exploring Social Barriers & Incentives to Social Licence

Fig. 12: The complete matrix of social risks and opportunities – Argentina.

Short Term, Low Impact

Opportunities:

- Employment and food security
- SME development/job creation (few)
- IMTA onshore/less visual impact

Short Term, Medium Impact

Risks:

- Visual impact

Opportunities:

- Fishing communities can incorporate new inhabitants required in these ventures
- Interest of residents in local natural resources
- Waste management
- Training for the diversification of the productive matrix
- Diversity of supply of new producers

Short Term, High Impact

Risks:

- Law or insufficient regulation (e.g., corruption, lack of punishment)
- Incompatibility with pre-existing activities (depends on the site where it is implemented) / Infrastructure necessary for IMTA operation

- Introduction of exotic/predatory or noxious species
- Everything related to aquaculture is associated with salmon farms and their respective impacts
- Conflicts in the use of space (for navigation / tourism) / Low quality of scenic values
- Incorrect interpretation of what IMTA implies by some sectors of society / Commercialization (local, national, international)
- Species escapes
- Eutrophication
- Risk of low circularity (closed system) / Excessive N and P inputs / Impact on benthos and commercial species / Contamination
- Impact on spoilage / Visual impact
- Organic pollution (due to changes in food web dynamics)
- Visual impact tourism (x 2)
- Inefficient monitoring (unilateral DDJJ)
- IMTA offshore / suspicion of environmental impact

Opportunities:

- Possibility of marketing a local product/Incentive to consume marine species
- Generation of work, food, both related to dignity
- Technological development
- Sustainable exploitation of resources
- Employment generation
- Environmental education regarding the different alternatives or forms of aquaculture
- IMTA on land; More control and less impact
- Dispersed information, deficient education in terms of marine culture
- Increased procurement of investments
- A good moment to be able to teach the general population about the possible benefits of this form of cultivation
- Meeting local gastronomic demand
- Local industrial development
- Productive capacities

Medium Term, Low Impact

Risks:

- Food safety

Opportunities:

- Direct/indirect employment
- Tourist attractions

Medium Term, Medium Impact

Risks:

- Technical management safety
- Tourism, landscape, odours
- Circular system takes a long time to stabilize, generating impacts during the transition
- Foreign capital = foreign profit
- Ambiental – Environmental
- Displacing small producers or resident workers by large non-local companies
- Deterioration of tourist attractions

Opportunities:

- Market penetration of new species
- Awareness that a productive activity can be conceived from the care of the environment
- Quality animal protein
- Jobs
- Local aquaculture development plus R&D knowledge → I+D

Medium Term, High Impact

Risks:

- Very low probability of efficient control (legislation/enforcement)
- Lack of enforcement authority
- Mismanagement of resources can negatively impact local opinion
- Rejection from other sectors (tourism) / Lack of economic promotion / Problems with sustainability of the enterprises
- Visual, chemical and biological pollution / interaction with marine fauna / energy consumption

Opportunities:

- Wealth generation
- Best aquaculture practices
- Linkage with gastronomy and tourism
- Generation of environmental awareness
- Economic development (employment and exports)
- Foreign exchange
- Opportunity to develop IMTA in a balanced and environmentally friendly way
- Job opportunities, creation of new jobs
- Local employment
- Regulatory approval of new species
- Product diversification
- Strengthening and development of environmental regulations

Long Term, Low Impact**Risks:**

- Habitat modification
- Minimal or minimised

Opportunities:

- Acceptable

Long Term, Medium Impact**Risks:**

- Exclusion of other activities
- Possible adverse effects on environmental impact
- Environmental

Opportunities:

- Labour that can be used subsidiarily for tourism
- Food health. Massive incorporation of seafood products

Long Term, High Impact**Risks:**

- Effects of extreme events on facilities
- Impact of tourism industry
- Poor control and/or regulation

Opportunities:

- Need to reconvert the productive matrix. Existence of researchers and professionals. Local professional training
- Diversification of the productive matrix
- Employment / Diversity of gastronomic producer offer / Tourism
- Generation of alternative energies (remote locations) / food security
- Positive interaction with tourism (attractive gastronomy) / Local value added / Education
- Food independence
- Opportunities for remediation
- Improve the image that the local society has regarding aquaculture
- Economic reactivation in small fishing localities
- Employment generation

Fig. 13: Participants at the Argentina workshop adding to the matrix for the risks and opportunities activity.

The completed matrix for Argentina (Fig. 12) shows that attendees to the ASTRAL Argentina workshop, as elsewhere, perceive IMTA as having potential to have a high impact on society. Many perceived risks and opportunities were identified by the Argentina workshop participants during this busy workshop session. Risks were considered to be greatest in both number and impact in the short term, diminishing over time. Opportunities remained strong throughout. These opportunities reflected the economic, environmental and employment hopes that had been echoed across all of the IMTA and society workshops series. Many of the risks, likewise, featured the regularly identified concerns relating to visual impact, poor regulation and possible negative environmental effects. One theme that stands out as distinctive to this region, however, is tourism, which was linked to both risks and opportunities. Ushuaia has a large tourism industry, and it is an important sector in the local economy. Several perceived risks were identified through this activity, specifically the deterioration of tourist attractions, conflict with tourism in use of space, the loss of scenic value through issues with visual impact and, finally, the impact of odours on tourism experiences. From the producer's perspective, it was also anticipated that there may be rejection of IMTA activities by the tourism sector, as it seeks to preserve its resources. On the positive side, there were perceived opportunities through incorporating IMTA in tourism, supplementing tourism labour, developing sites as educational tourism experiences and incorporating gastronomy in the region's tourism offerings.

3.3 Conclusion

In all workshops, the majority of risks/opportunities were placed in the medium or high impact sections. This suggests the participants at all workshops perceived IMTA as potentially having a medium to high impact on society, both in the positive and negative sense. In the Scotland and South Africa workshops, there was clear distinction in the timeframes in which these impacts were expected, with the risks spread quite evenly across the short, medium and long terms, and the opportunities not becoming apparent until the medium or long term. This suggests that in these regions, society is expected to bear the risks or costs of IMTA development before it might experience the opportunities and potential benefits of it. In Brazil, the benefits were anticipated to be apparent in the short term, but rising in impact as time progresses. Risks were apparent to the Brazil participants at all stages, but predominantly in the short term. The Argentina workshop participants were the only group to envisage the benefits being strongly apparent in all stages of IMTA development. They also anticipated the number and impact of risks would decrease as time progressed towards the longer term. The nature of the risk and opportunities identified were broadly similar in all of the regions, but with the addition of distinct local variations where applicable to the local economic or social landscape, for example the focus on skills in South Africa and the concerns for and opportunities with tourism in Argentina. This highlights that there are common factors to work on together, but also that local distinctions are significant and it is important to establish these with stakeholder groups on a case by case basis to ensure these local risks and opportunities are not overlooked.

The discussions in the Risks and Opportunities: Exploring Social Barriers and Incentives to Social Licence activity paved the way for the Social Licence to Operate guidelines activity later in the workshop.

4. Consumer Preferences

4.1 Method

This interactive activity measured consumer preferences for IMTA products. The aim was to create a space to quickly highlight the importance of this topic. By means of the Slido application, expectations that participants have regarding consumer preferences for IMTA products were explored. The Slido application is an easy tool to ask questions and to receive a live response from workshop participants.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Scotland

The first question (Fig. 14) regarded what factor participants consider most important for the IMTA exploitation of their products and had 9 participants. There was a heterogeneous opinion on this, with most (56%) of them selecting “the quality” and “it depends on the consumer” as the most important aspects for seafood consumers, with the origin being less relevant (33%) and price the lowest one (11%). This finding contradicts what some other quick surveys give as an answer to similar questions in aquaculture, where the price is also quite relevant together with the origin.

Fig. 14: Response to the first question in the consumer preferences activity – Scotland.

The second question (Fig. 15) was about algae consumption and had 11 participants. The participants shared their opinions, and here a bigger consensus was obtained. Almost three quarters of the participants (73%) were interested in introducing algae into their diets, and a smaller proportion, equating to 27%, thought it was important to know how to cook algae well to do so. 18% claimed they would only consume algae as like a supplement, and the lowest proportion (9%) thought that it is not necessary if you have a balanced diet.

Fig. 15: Response to the second question in the consumer preferences activity – Scotland.

Regarding algae, it is important to highlight the link that it has with the IMTA process and how it is planned to be exploited as a food product. Harvesting algae has important effects within the IMTA process and its bioremediation. At the moment, algae are not considered by European society as a product of routine consumption, but the EC are boosting their consumption as a more sustainable and healthier product. Concerns regarding public acceptance are on top. At the same time, the composition of the IMTA processes and its regulations are needed to provide food security and its interaction with the consumers acceptance should be explored.

The last question (Fig. 16) concerned eco-labels and was answered by 9 people. All (78% +22%) of participants shared the opinion that eco-labelling schemes are a good tool for product verification, and they will help despite the problems it may arise.

Fig. 16: Response to the third question in the consumer preferences activity – Scotland.

4.2.2 South Africa

The first question (Fig. 17) regarded what factor participants consider most important for the exploitation of IMTA products, and 22 took part. The participants had a heterogeneous opinion on this, with most of them (59%) attributing “it depends on the consumer” as the most important thing

Fig. 17: Response to the first question in the consumer preferences activity – South Africa.

for seafood consumers. “The quality” has relevance too at 36%, while “the price” is less relevant at 23%, and the lowest answer was “the origin” at 5%.

The second question (Fig. 18) is related to seaweed as a IMTA product and was answered by 23 people. The results show us participants’ willingness to introduce seaweed into their diets at 65%. Only a small proportion (26%) thought it best to introduce them solely as a supplement or that it was important to know how to cook algae well (17%). None thought that their diet could be healthy enough without it.

Fig. 18: Response to the second question in the consumer preferences activity – South Africa.

In response to the last question (Fig. 19), 60% of the 20 participants thought that eco-labels are a good tool or can be a tool to help and bring benefits to the company and to consumers. Another 20% thought of them as really useful and 20% did not know how to get started with the certification process. The lowest vote was related to price (10%), with respect to the high price of certification.

Fig. 19: Response to the third question in the consumer preferences activity – South Africa.

4.2.3 Brazil

The consumer preferences activity was conducted in-person for the first time at the Brazil workshop. Retaining the same format, it required participants to access the questionnaire via QR code or link.

Fig. 20: Daniel Checa Alias, Leitat Technological Institute, leading the consumer preferences activity in Brazil.

For the first question, on what factor they consider is more important for the IMTA exploitation of their products, the 6 participants had an unclear opinion about the most important thing for the seafood consumers. 100% thought that the final consumer should have the final decision but discussion in the room revealed views that it can be different based on the context (citizens preferences, supermarket availability, restaurant demand, etc.).

Fig. 21: Response to the first question in the consumer preferences activity – Brazil.

The second question regarded algae consumption and was answered by 5 people. The participants shared their opinions and here a large consensus was obtained, indicating that it is highly relevant. 80% of the participants were interested in introducing algae into their diets, and 20% thought it important to introduce it as a diet supplement.

Fig. 22: Response to the second question in the consumer preferences activity - Brazil

Regarding algae consumption, it is important to highlight the local context. At the moment, algae are not considered by Brazil society as a product of routine consumption, seafood has low demand from consumers and algae is even less common when talking about Brazilians' dietary habits.

The last question concerned certification and was answered by 6 people. 50% of participants had the same opinion on this issue, that eco-labelling certification schemes are a good tool for product verification and it will help despite any problems that may arise. 33% thought it would be useful for them, but they do not know how to use it, and 17% thought that an eco-label has no value in their perspective.

Fig. 23: Response to the third question in the consumer preferences activity - Brazil

4.2.4 Argentina

The first question (Fig. 24) was about what factor was considered most important for the exploitation of IMTA products. The 16 participants had a heterogeneous opinion in this regard, with the majority (56%) attributing "it depends on the consumer" as the most important for seafood consumers. For the participants, "quality" (19%), "origin" (13%) and "prices" (13%) had lower relevance.

Fig. 24: Response to the first question in the consumer preferences activity – Argentina.

The second question (Fig. 25) was about algae consumption and was answered by 17 of the attendees. Participants shared their opinions, and here we obtained heterogeneous answers, as in the first question. 35% of participants were interested in introducing seaweed into their diet, another 35% shared a similar opinion but did not know how to cook it. Another two blocks of 12% of participants voted for "Yes, but only as a supplement" and "No, I would prefer to eat fish two or more times a week." 6%, the smallest proportion, thought that it is not necessary if you have a balanced diet.

Fig. 25: Response to the second question in the consumer preferences activity – Argentina.

Currently, algae are not considered in Argentinean society as a product of routine consumption. First, they need a focus on taking advantage of their Atlantic coasts, to start Aquaculture projects, IMTA farms and other developments related to obtaining marine products. At the same time, the composition of IMTA's processes and their regulations are needed to provide food safety, and their interaction with consumer acceptance should be explored.

The last question (Fig. 26) concerned eco-labels and the certification process and recorded answers from 18 of the attendees. 50% of the participants had the same opinion on this topic, perceiving eco-labeling schemes to be a good tool for product verification. Another significant percentage of the participants (39%) thought that "Yes, it can increase their consumption". Two blocks of participants with 6% of the votes each were of the opinion that "I would like to, but I do not know the process of eco-labeling and certification related to this type of products" and "No, it is irrelevant".

Fig. 26: Response to the third question in the consumer preferences activity – Argentina.

5. Social Licence Guidelines

5.1 Method

As an introduction to the topic, a short presentation on Social Licence to Operate (SLO) was given, followed by an explanation of the exercise. SLO was described as an ongoing relationship between a host community and an organisation where the organisation is held to certain standards set by the community in exchange for trust and support. The basic case for SLO is to empower communities to engage with industry, so the costs of industrial activity are not solely on communities. SLO is also part of the evolution of social-ecological systems, where humans are seen as part of natural environmental system.

Industrial development is necessary to provide people with employment, income, goods and services – but it must take place in a way that is socially and environmentally sustainable. SLO can impact the viability of an operation through informal processes and can increase or decrease the reputational capital of an industry. It is important to understand the local situation, hence ASTRAL workshops at the different IMTA sites.

This activity aimed to produce draft guidelines for creating a positive relationship between the IMTA industry and society, that will lead to the provision of guidance on how to gain and maintain SLO for stakeholders already operating or seeking to operate IMTA sites. It is associated with *Task 7.6.2 Co-developing Interactive Guidelines*, for which the primary output is a set of social licence guidelines.

For the two online workshops (Scotland and South Africa), this was achieved through group discussion and the population of a word template, with categorization of the guidance under key headings. To ensure nothing was overlooked, at the end participants were asked if they would like to contribute any guidelines which had not been covered by the existing headings. For the two in-person workshops (Brazil and Argentina), participants were each issued three post-it notes and asked to write down guidelines for gaining and maintaining SLO for IMTA. Later in the workshop, after the results had been gathered and emergent themes identified, the suggested guidelines were discussed with the participants.

Fig. 27: Results of the social licence guidelines activity in Argentina.

Fig. 28: Laura Ferguson, SAMS, discusses the social licence activity with participants at the Argentina workshop.

The complete set of guidelines resulting from this activity at each workshop is provided in Section 5.2.

5.2 Results

5.2.1 Scotland

IMTA Social Licence to Operate Guidelines

Building Relationships and Inclusion

- They have to feel they are a part of it.
- Can we make them part of it – shareholders? Community buy-in? To give them an actual stake in the business.
- Engage environmental activists at an early stage – understand environmental benefits.
- Who is a stakeholder and how are they affected (directly or indirectly) and how do you weigh these?
- Mapping communities of place and communities of interest.
- A lot of communities are very organized and in touch with each other (esp. via social media). This makes it more difficult to work within than before.

Public Perceptions

- Lots of things sustainable environmentally that are not acceptable.
- Who is doing the developing is important to public perceptions (e.g., large multi-national). The activity may be the same, but who is undertaking it determines its acceptability.
- Talk about the whole process down to the local level to get around issues with multi-national.
- IMTA is an acceptability issue as much as a sustainability issue.
- Creating the right perception from the outset.
- Point out the environmental benefits and publish the EIA and have a thorough impact assessment.

Engagement Process and Style

- Is a meaningful process and is to listen to local views and take those into account.
- Social media now more important. Developers have to be more aware of social media.
- Openness and transparency – the whole story, warts and all.

Risk Assessment

- Utilisation of strong data that needs to underpin any impact assessment. Also, data sharing and transparency. Create a situation where people who need to share data can do so confidentially (e.g., fishing data).

Social Benefits

- Support local supply chains to bring benefits to local communities (esp. important for multi-nationals).

Evaluating Effectiveness

- Technology readiness level (links back to stakeholder mapping) – measure community readiness level to establish a baseline and measure through those parameters.
- Two social licences – development level (operator can probably judge) and industry level (more difficult to maintain and to measure – can be guided by a small number of people).
- Level of development and nature of development in particular places is a good measure (e.g. Shetland has a lot of aquaculture – seen as a part of the landscape, good relationship with communities).

5.2.2 South Africa

IMTA Social Licence to Operate Guidelines

Building Relationships and Inclusion

- Helps to have a different mechanism of engagement for different groups (e.g. face-to-face, language aspects, how they are affected).
- Build a stable relationship with community before even going into project.
- Clear objective between setting up the project and how they will benefit.
- Have a transparent relationship with stakeholders.
- Define what we mean by “communities.” Within any community of people there will be different stakeholder groups and different individuals with varying expectations/perceptions/background.

Public Perceptions

- Link public perceptions to social benefits.
- There may be an expectation that communities will have a share-holding in the business.

Engagement Process and Style

- Must be transparent and must not create false expectations.
- Keep at arm’s length – communities must think it is their project.
- Tailor the engagement style.

Risk Assessment

- Some may have resources for legal action.
- Skills set needed – do businesses have that skill set?

Social Benefits

- Include coastal communities in value chain.
- Future opportunities and current opportunities.

Evaluating Effectiveness

- Evaluate the relationship between you and them, and how the community is receiving it.

5.2.3 Brazil

IMTA Social Licence to Operate Guidelines

Policy and Regulation

- Controlled
- Public policies for development and implementation of the systems
- Involvement of the government for the producers to be interested in producing
- To set standards
- Governments should support IMTA system and make some favour about taxes for producers
- Decrease taxes
- Tax incentives when it's more sustainable (when sustainability goals are reached)

Environmental

- Sustainable system
- Options for places with little water and different temperatures
- Showing little environmental impact
- Focus on clean systems and renewable energies
- The impact of the system on the environment
- Environmental benefits, e.g., carbon sequestration
- It's an environmentally friendly activity (no antibiotics, less water)
- Use little area to do the system

Communication, Education and Public Involvement

- Promote the spread of popular knowledge about the systems
- Scientific dissemination accessible for the community
- Provide proven benefits
- Improve project information
- Public campaigns about IMTA production system benefits
- Educate: Provide information, provide evidence, answer questions, dispel myths
- Communication: Open, honest, appropriate level, point of contact
- Advertisement effect – global warming
- Open discussion with community
- Publicising the advantages of IMTA
- Dialogue with local communities
- Promote: sell benefits, show opportunities, highlight potential, contextualise alternatives
- Industry should share every step of production with society. Transparent production.
- Participation of local population in decision-making

Employment and Community Economic Advantages

- Including the local workforce
- Creating jobs for the community
- Specific courses focusing neighbourhood to be employed at IMTA farms
- Economic worth for the community
- Production of food for community accessible and competitive prices

Products

- Nutritional quality of the products
- Product diversification
- Quality of fish and shrimp produced

Research and Development

- Sharing of producers
- IMTA operational examples
- Incentive to research with IMTA in universities/production centres

5.2.4. Argentina

IMTA Social Licence to Operate Guidelines

Employment and Community Economic Advantages

- Generating quality employment/jobs
- Marketing and embedding local businesses

Environmental

- IMTA helps mitigate climate change with the seaweed harvesting and capture of CO₂
- 'Friendly' to the environment
- Diminution of contamination
- The recirculation of the nutrients of IMTA ensures a better conservation of the quality of water
- Use of autocrine species
- Advantages of the traditional harvesting methods

Communication, Education and Public Involvement

- + info + diffusion (broadcasting/promotion) + training
- Active presence of the company in the society
- Dissemination
- Strong presence of the scientific community
- Have clarity with the information to the population
- Informing of the risks and the actions to reduce them
- Adequate communication on aquaculture projects
- Social involvement
- Adequate expression of the risks of the project
- Environmental education
- Public education
- Active communication
- Providing clear and precise information about the advantages of IMTA, e.g., sustainability, circularity, harnessing/use
- Defending the impact continuously
- Easily accessible information
- Diffusion/broadcasting! (x3) information about risks and how to mitigate them
- Sharing information
- The society knows the production activity
- Knowing the benefits for the society

- Communication about the numbers of project: investment vs profit ratio (number of jobs that can be created, etc.)
- Quantifying the expected benefits, employment for example
- As a 1st step, education – communication – dissemination about the concepts of IMTA and circularity
- Certifications and participation in workshops
- Knowledge of the system (training)
- Benefits: circularity-employment-local resources
- Training, expanding knowledge related to aquaculture
- Medium term, the success of the initiative will be the best publicity for the project

Policy and Regulation

- Good regulation
- Clarity of the offer in local language
- Prestige of the moderator/organizer, socially recognised
- Rules of the game
- Promoting socio-environmentally appropriate regulatory frameworks
- Products
- Improvement of food security
- Possibility to consume fresh local products
- IMTA supports/encourages valorisation of local products and their entrance to market
- Opportunities to expand the productive matrix
- Incorporating it as 'attractive' for local tourism
- Fair (event/festival) of sea produce

Qualities/Behaviours

- Transparency
- Generating trust
- Led by local actors
- Local managers with known and accepted track record
- Predictability
- No interference with other activities (tourism, fishing)
- Considering the actors of the territory where IMTA is carried out

5.3 Conclusion

The guidance emerging from the four ASTRAL regional workshops is the first step in the co-creation of SLO guidelines that are intended to be used by IMTA producers to gain SLO and ensure that social concerns are embedded in site development from the outset.

The outputs from the individual workshops have been combined. Next, the full collection of guidelines will be sense-checked with an expert board comprised of international experts in research and innovation, environmental protection, civic engagement policies, social innovation and community movements, formed in accordance with *Task 7.6.3 Steering the Knowledge and Sharing Process Within and Outside ASTRAL*, for review and final selection and categorization. This process will result in the definitive set of co-created guidelines on SLO for IMTA, as specified in *Task 7.6.2 Co-developing Interactive Guidelines*.

The expert panel will be formed in conjunction with Work Package 1 activities, and the final set of guidelines for SLO will subsequently be published and disseminated through the Aquaculture Helix by the end of the project.

6. Policy

6.1 Method

The policy session was developed through Goggle Jamboard. The first step involved providing participants with a description of the activity. Then, a few potential issues regarding IMTA policy were raised. These topics generated debate between the participants where they shared their opinions.

Fig. 29: The policy activity Jamboard.

Through a group discussion, participants began to create their own labels regarding IMTA policy, and then placed the labels on the side of the board where they thought the label was most appropriate, classifying the degree of the potential issues and relevance. For the in-person workshops, the participants wrote onto a note and then they pasted the notes to be positioned on the board, as illustrated in Figure 30, and the results were afterwards transcribed to Goggle Jamboard. Below are the final results for each workshop, after the discussion and the classification.

Fig. 30: Joel Armengol Pagès, Leitai Technological Institute, leads the policy discussion as Tomás Chalde, CADIC-CONICET, positions notes on the board.

6.2 Results

6.2.1 Scotland

Fig. 31: Completed policy Jamboard for Scotland.

When the contributions were organised into the four boxes, the participants decided on the following factors:

Look for opportunities to use

- Bioremediation
- Aesthetic impact
- Life cycle analysis and carbon capture
- Environmental monitoring within local regulations, e.g. SEPA
- Regulation around products from IMTA – will IMTA impose limitations
- Learn from other places
- Multi-species licence application
- Lack of circularity methodologies for the biological nutrient remediation

Keep on the Radar

- IMTA licence procedure
- Process extremely complicated – should be made simpler
- Climate change
- Reactive rather than proactive
- Licencing authorities

Consider later

- Health and hygiene management
- Medicine restrictions
- Natura 2000

Do not consider

- None

6.2.2 South Africa

Fig. 32: Completed policy Jamboard for South Africa.

Once the different contributions were separated into the four boxes, the participants identified the following factors:

Look for opportunities to use

- Investment into commercial aquaculture
- Climate change benefits, e.g., seaweed
- Scalability
- Market
- Existing IMTA policies in different countries
- Genetic impacts

Keep on the Radar

- Bureaucratic processes
- Bureaucratic processes in obtaining research permits for new species
- Common and harmonised IMTA policies through different geographical areas
- Food safety
- Diseases
- Health and hygiene management
- Multi-species licence application
- Reliable supply
- Biosecurity
- Organised labour
- IMTA licence procedure

- New methodologies to assess circularity in aquaculture

Consider later

- Ecosystem services
- Capacity development around aquaculture third party auditors
- Carbon and/or nitrogen credits

Do not consider

- None

6.2.3 Brazil

The policy activity was conducted slightly differently in Brazil from the other three workshops. Discussion took place around three groups of 4-5 people. Each group pointed out the main potential issues in relation with aquaculture and IMTA, then a further analysis of them was conducted by the same participants in order to classify those issues in a matrix considering the potential for improvement and the difficulty in terms of implementation.

The first group detected as potential issues the effluent emission, manglers destruction, antibiotic waste, disease in aquatic organisms and conflicts with other activities (tourism, fishing, etc). Effluent emissions was considered as an opportunity to use, improving the quality of the effluents while producing other species under the IMTA concept. Manglers destruction, antibiotic waste, disease in aquatic organisms were detected as issues to keep on the radar, with high potential of improvement but low implementation. Conflicts with other activities whas classified in the “consider later” box.

Fig. 33: Policy matrix for Brazil Group 1.

The second group detected as potential issues the animal genetics in aquaculture (GMO/ gene editing) that is not allowed in Europe, and lack of regulation and the unavailability to track data. Both potential issues were classified as “keep on radar” due its high potential of improvement but low implementation potential.

Fig. 34: Policy matrix for Brazil Group 2.

The third group's potential issues were the lack of knowledge about aquaculture from population, environmental awareness, lack of extension services, conflicts of interest, water depletion, aquatic species exploitation, lack of qualified governmental personnel. The rest of the issues were placed under "keep on radar" due to high potential of improvement but low implementation potential.

Fig. 35: Policy matrix for Brazil Group 3.

6.2.4. Argentina

Fig. 36: Completed policy Jamboard for Argentina.

The four Google Jamboard blocks, with the notes written by the participants are as below.

Look for opportunities to use

- Lack of political knowledge x2
- Overly lax laws that prioritize economic benefits over the environment, e.g., sustainability over time
- Apathy and social fatigue
- Lack of incentives to start the activity
- Regulations that are slow to be implemented and enforced
- Lack of technical assistance

Keep on the Radar

- Historically in Tierra del Fuego; *Lack of regulation in aquaculture. *Lack of audit control (x2)
- Lack of a sustainable master plan
- Prohibition policies lead to stagnation of aquaculture activity
- Uninformed decisions
- Lack of policy makers with a local perspective that addresses local needs and potentials
- Different legislation in shared areas
- Volatility of governments leads them to deliberately change policy
- Curbing imports
- That many obstacles are put in the way and the project is frustrated. *Bureaucratic and momentary interests
- Control difference
- Unbridled profit
- Participation of scientists restricted to their field
- Corruption and embezzlement (x2)
- That more electioneering objectives are being pursued than those of real interest to society
- 2023 Elections
- Non-compliance with laws and lack of control and/or "punishment"
- Decisions not based on scientific evidence/data
- Lack of policy continuity when management changes
- Lack of medium-term predictability
- Excessive prohibitions
- Risk of contradictory policies at different levels of government, e.g. Provincial and National
- Lack of political and governmental support
- Restrictive and non-specific regulation
- Lack of control in the activity leading to environmental and/or social impact. *Lack of legislation
- Risk of non-enforcement or non-monitoring of the law
- Lack of regulations to promote aquaculture
- Flexibilisation of monitoring
- Lack of incentives

Consider later

- Lack of financial support for aquaculture projects

Do not consider

- None

The results of the policy workshop will be used to make an assessment of the current policy situation in each IMTA lab country, including gaps, opportunities, dangers, etc. *Task 7.7 Studies on Governance, Policy, Food Safety/Consumer Trust and Social Acceptability* will be an opportunity to obtain more policy related results. The interviews will provide an additional point of view, and with both results combined the insights and conclusions will be more comprehensive and objective.

7. Conclusion and Next Steps

This report described the assessment of public perceptions and awareness of IMTA at four ASTRAL IMTA Lab sites that was conducted through the ASTRAL IMTA and Society series of workshops, in fulfilment of *Task 7.6.1 Participatory Workshops*. As a result, the ASTRAL project has gained a better understanding of social perceptions of IMTA that will be useful in developing socially acceptable IMTA sites, and communities and other stakeholders have been able to engage with IMTA development and communicate their expectations, hopes and concerns associated with it.

The workshops were attended by a broad variety of stakeholders, including local NGOs, community members, regulatory agencies, politicians and producers. The ASTRAL project team are incredibly grateful for the contributions of participants to this work on societal impacts of IMTA. The discussions relating to the activities were engaging and informative.

In the process, they have contributed to four social tasks in the ASTRAL project, in public perceptions and awareness (*Task 7.6.1 Participatory Workshops*), Social Licence to Operate (*Task 7.6.2 Co-developing Interactive Guidelines*), consumer preferences (*Task 7.7 Studies on Governance, Policy, Food Safety/Consumer Trust and Social Acceptability*) and policy analysis (*Task 7.7 Studies on Governance, Policy, Food Safety/Consumer Trust and Social Acceptability*). Their views will feed into the outputs of these tasks over the remainder of the project, be further analysed and disseminated through scientific journal articles and ultimately inform understanding of the societal aspects of IMTA.

This report outlines results and initial analysis from the two core social perceptions activities, the risks and opportunities matrix (Section 3) and the social licence guidelines creation (Section 5). Results from these activities will be subject to further thematic analysis at SAMS and, in due course, published. A further workshop in connection with these activities is planned for September 2023. This workshop will focus on a single geographic community in a coastal area familiar with aquaculture and close to an ASTRAL IMTA Lab. It will assess public awareness and perceptions of IMTA among the general public that live and work specifically in this area and will comprise a series of bespoke activities designed to assess attitudes among members of the public with a connection to the coastal area but not necessarily to the aquaculture industry or marine regulation/management. This will complement the results of the national workshops that have been informed by a wide variety of experts and interested groups.

The results of the consumer preferences and policy activities will be taken forward by Leitao Technological Institute and analysed and published in accordance with their tasks and dissemination aims.

A significant direct output of the workshops is that stakeholders have contributed to the first stage in producing a co-created set of guidelines for IMTA producers to obtain SLO, which will ensure that social concerns are embedded in site development from the outset and encourage a good relationship between the IMTA industry and society. These will be sense-checked with an expert board comprised of international experts in 2023 and subsequently published and disseminated through the Aquaculture Helix.

ASTRAL Workshop Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture and Society

**22nd October 2021
10:00-12:30**

- | | |
|-------------|--|
| 10:00-10:05 | Welcome and introductions |
| 10:05-10:20 | Introduction to the ASTRAL project |
| 10:20-10:50 | Risks and opportunities – exploring social barriers and incentives |
| 10:50-11:00 | Consumer preferences for IMTA produce |
| 11:00-11:15 | Break |
| 11:15-11:45 | Co-creation of social licence guidelines |
| 11:45-12:20 | IMTA policy |
| 12:20-12:30 | Close of workshop and how to stay updated and involved |

ASTRAL Workshop Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture and Society

**15 February 2022
14:00-16:30**

- 14:00-14:05 Welcome and introductions
- 14:05-14:25 Introduction to the ASTRAL project and IMTA Lab
- 14:25-14:55 Risks and opportunities – exploring social barriers and incentives
- 14:55-15:10 Consumer preferences for IMTA produce
- 15:10-15:25 Break
- 15:25-15:45 Co-creation of social licence guidelines
- 15:45-16:20 IMTA policy
- 16:20-16:30 Close of workshop and how to stay updated and involved

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863034

ASTRAL Workshop Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture and Society

**31st August 2022
14:00-18:00**

- 14:00-14:10 Welcome and Introduction to the ASTRAL project
- 14:10-14:30 30-second round the room introductions
- 14:30-14:45 ASTRAL in Brazil
- 14:45-15:30 Risks and opportunities – exploring social barriers and incentives
- 15:30-15:40 Co-creation of social licence guidelines (part 1)
- 15:40-15:55 Aquaculture Helix and how to stay updated and involved
- 15:55-16:05 Break
- 16:05-16:20 Consumer preferences for IMTA produce results
- 16:20-17:20 Aquaculture policy
- 17:20-17:30 Co-creation of social licence guidelines (part 2)
- 17:30-17:40 David Basset, General Secretary of EATiP
- 17:40-18:00 Questions and answers

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ASTRAL Workshop Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture and Society

8th November 2022, 08:45-13:00

Centro Austral de Investigaciones Científicas, Bernardo Houssay 200, Ushuaia, Argentina

- 08:45-09:00** **Registration**
- 09:00-09:10** **Welcome and Introduction to the ASTRAL project**
Tomás Chalde, CADIC-CONICET, and Elisa Ravagnan, Norwegian Research Center
- 09:10-09:30** **30-second round the room introductions**
- 09:30-09:45** **ASTRAL in Argentina**
Tomás Chalde, CADIC-CONICET, Argentina
- 09:45-10:30** **Risks and opportunities – exploring social barriers and incentives**
Laura Ferguson, Scottish Association for Marine Science
- 10:30-10:40** **Co-creation of social licence guidelines (part 1)**
Laura Ferguson, Scottish Association for Marine Science
- 10:40-10:55** **Aquaculture Helix and how to stay updated and involved**
Laura Ferguson, Scottish Association for Marine Science
- 10:55-11:05** **Break**
- 11:05-11:20** **Consumer preferences for IMTA produce**
Joel Armengol Pagès, Leitat Technological Center
- 11:20-12:20** **Aquaculture policy**
Joel Armengol Pagès, Leitat Technological Center
- 12:20-12:30** **Co-creation of social licence guidelines (part 2)**
Laura Ferguson, Scottish Association for Marine Science
- 12:30-13:00** **Questions and answers**

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Appendix V: Workshop invitation email template (edited and translate into local language for each event).

Dear [NAME],

I am writing from the [INSTITUTION] to invite you to the ASTRAL project workshop on society and Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) taking place [LOCATION/ONLINE] on [DATE] at [TIME].

The All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) project (<https://www.astral-project.eu/>) is a Horizon 2020 European-funded project that focuses on IMTA farming and defines, supports and promotes this type of sustainable aquaculture production in the Atlantic area.

The [INSTITUTION] is a partner in the ASTRAL project. Our experimental offshore farm at [IMTA LAB LOCATION] is being used to develop and test a wide range of cultivation approaches seeking to efficiently combine [SPECIES 1] and [SPECIES 2] cultivation. By validating an effective approach, we aim to facilitate the future expansion of similar IMTA models.

This event will be the first opportunity for interested stakeholders in the area to engage with the ASTRAL project and find out more about it. The programme includes a mix of presentations, discussions and interactive activities. The views collected will be used to develop a set of social licence guidelines to support best practice in engaging local stakeholders and establishing social licence to operate.

The workshop will last [NUMBER] hours, and will be attended by a variety of local stakeholders, including community members, local NGOs, businesses and organisations operating close to the site, planning and environmental officers, political representatives, investors and consumers.

To join, please reply to this email to confirm by [DATE – 1 WEEK BEFORE WORKSHOP].

If you have any questions about the workshop or the ASTRAL project, please contact me on [CONTACT'S EMAIL ADDRESS].

Best wishes,
[CONTACT'S NAME]

Appendix VI: Workshop online link email template (for online workshops).

Dear [NAME],

The Teams link below will give you access to the ASTRAL Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture and Society workshop on [DATE], [TIME].

[LINK]

Please find attached the agenda, participant information sheet, data privacy statement and a consent form. The consent form is in order to record the workshop, which is necessary as it is not going to be possible to take sufficient notes during discussion segments while chairing them. The recording will not be shown anywhere and will only be held long enough to transcribe the discussions. Anyone who prefers is welcome to switch their camera off if it makes them more comfortable. The attached documents explain the recording in full.

I would be grateful if you could please sign and return the consent form by [WORKSHOP DAY].

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to get in contact. I look forward to seeing you virtually on [WORKSHOP DAY].

Best wishes,
[CONTACT'S NAME]

Appendix VII: Participant Information Sheet

What is the purpose of the workshop?

This workshop contributes to the ASTRAL (All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture) project, which aims to define, support and promote integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) farming. The main purpose of the workshop is to understand social licence and how to obtain and maintain it. It will incorporate the key task of developing social licence guidelines. In addition, there will be activities relating to policy and consumer preferences.

Who is organising and funding the study?

The workshop is being hosted by the [INSTITUTION] and the data is being processed by the Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS). This study is undertaken as part of the ASTRAL project in which the [INSTITUTION] and the Scottish Association for Marine Science are partners. The funder of the study is the EU Horizon 2020 programme.

Why have I been chosen to take part?

We are interested in the views of stakeholders, including community members, NGOs, businesses/organisations operating in the area, planning/environmental officers, political representatives, investors and consumers, on social aspects of IMTA. You have been selected for invitation because we feel you have a particular contribution to make to the debate on social licence to operate in aquaculture.

What will I be asked to do?

You will be involved in a series of group discussion-based activities relating to social aspects of IMTA, as detailed in the accompanying workshop agenda. You do not have to take part in any activity you feel you cannot or do not wish to contribute to.

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Will my participation be recorded?

For the purposes of analysing the activities, the workshop will be recorded, however the recording will only be accessible to the project researchers and footage from it will not be publicly distributed. The recording will be stored securely on SAMS servers and will be deleted on completion of transcription.

Do I have to give consent to take part?

Yes. If you decide to participate you will be asked to sign the accompanying consent form, as the workshop audio will be recorded for research purposes.

What are the possible benefits of participating?

By taking part you will be contributing to a piece of research which is seeking to promote IMTA across the Atlantic area. You will also get the opportunity to learn about ASTRAL and social subjects that it covers, engage with the project, and meet researchers and stakeholders with an interest in IMTA.

What are the possible disadvantages to my taking part?

We do not anticipate that there will be any disadvantages and participation is entirely voluntary.

What will happen to the results of the study?

The results will be written up in project reports and a set of social licence guidelines. They may also contribute to journal articles and conference papers. Any information taken from the workshop will be anonymised in publication.

What happens if I change my mind or want to withdraw from the study?

You have a right to decline the invitation or to withdraw at any time without providing an explanation or incurring any penalty. However, it may not be possible to remove your data from the project once it has been anonymised and aggregated, and therefore we ask you to communicate any request to withdraw your data needs to laura.ferguson@sams.ac.uk within a week of the workshop, to allow us to identify and delete any data you provided to the project. Your decision to withdraw does not affect your data protection rights.

What are my rights in relation to the information you will collect about me?

You have a number of rights under data protection law regarding your personal information. These include the right to withdraw consent, the right to access your personal data, the right to rectification if the personal data

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we hold about you is incorrect, the right to restrict processing of your personal data, and the right to request erasure (deletion) of your personal data. The right to data portability and the right to object to our processing of your personal data apply only in certain circumstances. A data privacy statement accompanies this information sheet in your workshop information email. For any queries or concerns about how your personal data is being processed you can contact the Data Privacy Manager at DPE@sams.ac.uk.

Will my personal identifiable information be protected?

In accordance with data protection law, the Data Controller of the information being collected is the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scottish Marine Institute, Oban, Argyll, PA37 1QA. Phone: 01631 559000). This means that SAMS is responsible for making sure your personal information is kept secure, confidential and used only in the way you have been told it will be used. All researchers are trained with this responsibility in mind, all information you supply will be anonymised, with names or any identifiable information not attached to workshop transcriptions. Anonymised transcripts will be only accessible and controlled by the project researchers at SAMS.

What if something goes wrong or what if I have a complaint?

It is extremely unlikely that something will go wrong during this workshop. However, you should know that SAMS/UHI have procedures in place for reporting, investigating, recording and handling adverse events and complaints from study participants. The University/Institute are insured for its staff to carry out research involving human participants. The University/Institute know about this research project and have approved it following a rigorous ethical review process by UHI Research Ethics Committee. Any complaint should be made, in the first instance, to the principal investigator Prof. Michele Stanley (Michele.Stanley@sams.ac.uk). If you wish to make a formal complaint to someone independent of the research team or if you are not satisfied with the response you have gained from the researchers in the first instance, then please contact Research Ethics Officer fiona.leiper@uhi.ac.uk. If you wish to contact us about your data protection rights, please email the Data Privacy Manager at DPE@sams.ac.uk, who will guide you through the process of exercising your rights. You also have the right to lodge a complaint with the Information Commissioner's Office about our handling of your personal identifiable information. For more information about ICO's role, please consult www.ico.org.uk or call 0303 123 1113.

Who has reviewed the study?

[ADD LOCAL INSTITUTION DETAILS]. The study has also been reviewed and granted approval by the Research Ethical Committee of University of the Highlands and Islands, of which the Scottish Association for Marine Science is an academic partner.

Will my contact details be shared with other participants?

We will not be sharing contact details with other participants. If you wish to share contact details with any other participants you engage with on the day, we suggest you do so during the workshop.

Can I invite someone else who may be interested?

Yes, if you know someone who may like to contribute we encourage you to extend the invitation to them. All we ask is that they contact [LOCAL CONTACT NAME] on [CONTACT EMAIL ADDRESS] in advance to receive a link to the meeting and a consent form.

Who can I contact for more information?

Should you require any more information, please contact [LOCAL CONTACT NAME] on [CONTACT EMAIL ADDRESS].

Thank you for taking time to read this information sheet.

ASTRAL Workshop: Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture & Society

[DATE], [TIME]

Appendix VIII: Participant Consent

Please tick box

- 1. I confirm that I have been given and have read and understand the information sheet for the above workshop. I have had the opportunity to ask and receive answers to any questions I may have had. []
- 2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw up to one week from the date of the workshop, without giving reason. []
- 3. I agree to take part in this workshop. []
- 4. I agree to being recorded as part of the workshop to facilitate analysis. []

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Name of Researcher

Date

Signature

One copy for the Researcher and one copy for the Participant

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